

United States Department of the Interior

FISH AND WILDLIFE SERVICE
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In Reply Refer to:
2025-010407-S7

August 28, 2025
Sent Electronically

Winnie Chan
Conservation Planner
San Francisco Bay National Wildlife Refuge Complex
U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service
1 Marshlands Rd
Fremont, CA 94555
Winnie_chan@fws.gov

Subject: Section 7 Consultation on the Ignacio-Mare Island 115 Kilovolt (kV) Tower Replacement Phase 4 Project, Unincorporated Solano County, California

Dear Winnie Chan:

This letter is in response to the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service's National Wildlife Refuge System's (Refuge System) August 5, 2025, request for initiation of formal consultation with the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service's Ecological Services (Service) on the proposed Ignacio-Mare Island 115 Kilovolt (kV) Tower Replacement Phase 4 Project (proposed project) in unincorporated Solano County, California. Your request was received by the Service on August 5, 2025. At issue are the proposed project's effects on the federally endangered California Ridgway's rail (*Rallus obsoletus obsoletus*), the federally endangered salt marsh harvest mouse (*Reithrodontomys raviventris*), and the federally threatened California red-legged frog (*Rana draytonii*). This response is provided under the authority of the Endangered Species Act of 1973, as amended (16 U.S.C. 1531 *et seq.*) (Act) and in accordance with the implementing regulations pertaining to agency cooperation (50 CFR 402).

The federal action on which we are consulting is the issuance of a right-of-way permit by the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service's San Francisco Bay National Wildlife Refuge Complex, to Pacific Gas and Electric Company (PG&E) for the replacement or modification of eight aging existing transmission towers along its Ignacio-Mare Island 115kV transmission line on the San Pablo Bay National Wildlife Refuge.

Pursuant to 50 CFR 402.12(j), you submitted a biological constraints report for our review and requested concurrence with the findings presented therein. These findings conclude that the proposed project may affect and is likely to adversely affect the California Ridgway's rail, salt marsh harvest mouse, and California red-legged frog. You have stated that the proposed project is a covered activity in the PG&E Bay Area Habitat Conservation Plan (Plan). You have also stated that the California Ridgway's rail, salt marsh harvest mouse, and California red-legged frog are covered species under the Plan.

In considering your request, we based our evaluation on the following:

- 1) Information provided in the consultation request dated August 5, 2025;
- 2) The Plan dated September 2017;
- 3) The July 18, 2025, Biological Constraints Report for Ignacio-Mare Island 115 Kilovolt (kV) Tower Replacement Phase 4 Project (report);
- 4) The August 21, 2025 project meeting between PG&E, Refuge, and Ecological Services staff; and
- 5) Other information available to the Service.

As described in the information submitted to the Service, the proposed project is covered under the Plan. The proposed project corresponds to the Tower and Boardwalk Replacement or Repair covered activity under the Operation and Maintenance Covered Activities for the Electric System section described in the Plan. The proposed project, if implemented as described in the report, complies with all applicable conditions required by the Plan and ITP, and our 2017 intra-Service biological opinion (Service File Number 08ESMF00-2013-F-0102-04; biological opinion). The status of the California Ridgeway's rail, salt marsh harvest mouse, and California red-legged frog and the effects of covered activities, such as the proposed project, were previously addressed in our biological opinion. In the biological opinion, we concluded that the effects of the covered activities and level of incidental take were not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the California Ridgeway's rail, salt marsh harvest mouse, and California red-legged frog. As a result, the Service authorized the incidental take associated with the proposed project in the Plan's incidental take permit (Service Permit Number 08ESMF00-2013-F-0102-04, issued on September 28, 2017; ITP).

Given that the proposed project is consistent with the Plan, we do not anticipate any adverse effects to the California Ridgeway's rail, salt marsh harvest mouse, and California red-legged frog that were not previously evaluated in the biological opinion.

This fulfills the Refuge System's requirement to consult with the Service under section 7 of the Act. As provided in 50 CFR 402.16(a), reinitiation of formal consultation is required and shall be requested by the federal agency where discretionary federal involvement or control over the action has been retained or is authorized by law, and if:

- 1) The amount or extent of taking specified in the incidental take statement is exceeded;
- 2) New information reveals effects of the action that may affect listed species or critical habitat in a manner or to an extent not previously considered;
- 3) The identified action is subsequently modified in a manner that causes an effect to the listed species or critical habitat that was not considered in the biological opinion or written concurrence; or
- 4) A new species is listed or critical habitat designated that may be affected by the identified action.

If you have any questions regarding this letter, please contact Bridget Giblin, Fish and Wildlife Biologist (bridget_giblin@fws.gov) or at (916) 414-6624 or Ryan Olah, Coast Bay Division Supervisor (ryan_olah@fws.gov), at (916) 414-6623.

Sincerely,

Ryan Olah
Coast-Bay Division Supervisor

cc:

David Thomas, Pacific Gas & Electric, San Francisco, California

Ode Bernstein, Pacific Gas & Electric, Oakland, California

Melisa Amato, U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service Refuge System, Fremont, California